

USE OF WATER RESERVOIR IN EMERGENCIES RESERVOIR OVERFLOW PREDICTION AND PREVENTION

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It is worth noting that sometimes there are opinions that: "Even if the reservoir is full at the time of the flood, the water transfer structures have the ability to handle even the smallest possible large flood." But in such extreme conditions, water transfer is very dangerous, and unpleasant or accidental situations can occur in structures, especially in the lower part. For example, erosion of concrete or metal coatings, failure of mechanical equipment, washing of the bottom floor, etc.

During a heavy downpour, if the reservoir is filled to the maximum, in order to prevent the water level in the reservoir from rising, it is necessary to quickly empty it and take measures to bring the amount of water in the reservoir to a safe level.

In practice, there are cases that are contrary to the above idea, that is, they are afraid of the overflow of the reservoir, and on the eve of the flood, they release more water than the norm, and as a result, they fail to reach the maximum volume of water that can be collected in the reservoir.

Thus, in order to prevent the reservoir from overflowing, to safely transfer the required amount of water to the structures and the bottom of the flood, to collect as much water as possible, a break line and a filling limit line, which is a part of it, will be built.

Reservoir overflow can occur when the water level in the reservoir exceeds the reservoir fill limit line near the peak of the flood.

In order to prevent the reservoir from overflowing, it is necessary to monitor the mark of the water level in it from the beginning of the year and compare it with the mark of the boundary line of filling the reservoir. This comparison should be made at least once at the end of each month at the beginning and end of the year, at the end of every ten days during the flood, and daily at the peak of the flood.

The mark of the water level in the reservoir cannot be higher than the mark of the boundary line of filling the reservoir. If it is high, then it is necessary to lower the water level to the boundary line of filling the reservoir.

For this, it is necessary to increase the water output in accordance with the difference in signs, that is;

$$\Delta Q = 77 (\nabla_{\text{shown}} - \nabla_{\text{along the line}}). \quad (1)$$

Use of facilities in emergency situations

During a natural flood caused by a sudden flash flood in the reservoir, all the structures are subjected to a large amount of stress, so it is impossible to allow a large amount of excess water consumption in the water supply channel.

In the event of floods, preparations for the transfer of flood flows are carried out by developing a series of measures.

The action plan is drawn up based on pre-determined basic data on the nature, timing, and size of floods and floods.

During the preparation period, the following should be done:

- completion of construction repair works;
- checking the stock of materials for the accident;
- to prepare vehicles and equipment;
- to be in constant contact with the head of the channel and organize night lighting in dangerous places;
- organization of a team of workers and the duty of engineers and technicians based on the schedule.

After the transfer of flood and flood waters, it is necessary to identify, clean and carry out other repair and restoration works of the damaged areas of the rainwater discharge facility and channel.

It is necessary to temporarily block the area where restoration and repair works are being carried out.

Transfer of flood and catastrophic water consumption:

When floods and strong currents are expected, the operation service is required to work quickly.

The Hydrometeorological Service Organization (Uzgidromet) warns the Ministry of Water Management about heavy rains and sudden floods, and provides information even during heavy rains and floods. As soon as the hydrometeorological service receives warning information from the organization, a reserve volume for stormwater is stored without filling the reservoir to the maximum level.

During flash floods, the water level in the reservoir and downstream, the amount of water passing through the spillway, and the condition of the dam are monitored around the clock. At the same time, the following cases are monitored:

- subsidence or other forms of deformation;
- appearance of cracks;
- damage to coatings;
- erosion of slopes and destruction of banks;
- comparison of the filtration from the base of the structures and passing through it with the design;
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- accumulation of muddy sediments in the territory of the water outlet;
- monitoring the normality of the water level. During flash floods, the water level in the reservoir and downstream, the amount of water passing through the spillway, and the condition of the dam are monitored around the clock. At the same time, the following cases are monitored:
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- accumulation of muddy sediments in the territory of the water outlet;
 - - monitoring the normality of the water level.

After carrying out the catastrophic water consumption, the condition of the facilities is inspected. If malfunctions are detected, a repair-recovery schedule is drawn up, and repair-recovery activities are carried out based on this schedule. Total repair and restoration work will be completed for next year's flood season.

In case of emergency, spare materials and tools - equipment, equipment needed for repair work should be prepared based on the list (Table 1). The list of spare materials, tools and equipment needed for emergency repairs is prepared together with the head of the reservoir of each department of the reservoir and agreed with the Jizzakh Region Reservoir Utilization Department.

Winter mode: The use of Novka water reservoir facilities in winter conditions has a special feature, in which it is prevented from freezing and the formation of ice streams. It is not recommended to raise the water level of the reservoir above the ice-covered level during the severe winter season when the water surface is frozen. If the water level is 1001.5 m or higher when the freezing process begins in the reservoir, the water level in the reservoir should

be lowered immediately. It is necessary to ensure that the rate of lowering the water level of the reservoir does not exceed the standard level in order not to damage the pressure slopes when lowering the water level of the reservoir. After the ice in the reservoir melts, the water level of the reservoir can be raised.

In order to prevent freezing of the canal slopes and the walls of the structures in the winter period, it is not recommended to change the water level in the water-carrying canal.

Table 1. A list of spare materials, tools and equipment needed for emergency repairs.

No	Naming	Unit of measure	Amount
1	All kinds of sanded wood	m ³	3
2	Sorted gravel	m ³	15
3	Washed sand	m ³	10
4	Cement	t	5
5	6 mm to 20 mm rebar	t	1
6	Schweller, ugolok (various types)	t	1
7	3-5 mm wires	t	1
8	All kinds of nails	kg	20
9	Various ropes	p/m	10
10	Tarpaulin	m ²	50
11	Bags	piece	150
12	Various ropes	kg	20
13	Hemp	kg	30
Metal construction and equipment			
1	A variety of roulette	piece	5
2	Metal cart	piece	4
3	Chukchi	piece	4
4	Lom	piece	4
5	Stretcher	piece	5
6	Ax	piece	2
7	Saw	piece	4
8	Bucket	piece	10
9	A sharp shovel	piece	10
10	Flat spade	piece	10
11	Projector	piece	4
12	Welding equipment	piece	2

13	Electric lamp	piece	10
14	Copy lantern	piece	4
15	Pump	comp	2
16	Water tank	piece	5
Electric equipment, equipment and automatic tools			
1	The last switch	piece	1
2	Gate position sensor	piece	2
3	Reversible magnetic inserter	piece	1
4	Three-pole circuit breaker	piece	1
5	Double pole circuit breaker	piece	1
6	electric button	piece	2
7	Relay	piece	1
8	Step-down transformer	piece	1
9	Electric connector	piece	1

Organization of water reservoir operation by performing the above measures will be highly effective in using the water reservoir in emergency situations. and reliable and safe use of water reservoirs is achieved.

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